

THE MAIN PURPOSE OF AUDIO-VISUAL TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Pulatova Nodirabegim Bakhtiyarovna

*senior teacher Department of "Pedagogy and Psychology"
of Tashkent Social Innovations University*

Abstract: This paper focus on how to use audio-visual tools in teaching of technical courses in English language. The main purpose of audio-visual aids is to enable the teachers to make his teaching effective and interesting. Good models are presented before the students to teach effectively. In this way it can be said that audio-visual aids direct sensory experience to the students.

Key words: audio-visual tools, communication skills, technical knowledge, advanced visual aids, audio-visual equipment, educational world, emotional impact

Izoh: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilida muhandislik kurslarini o'rgatishda audiovizual vositalardan qanday foydalanishga qaratilgan. Audiovizual vositalarning asosiy maqsadi o'qituvchiga darsni samarali va qiziqarli o'tkazishga imkon berishdir. Talabalarga samarali o'rganish uchun yaxshi modellar taqdim etiladi. Shunday qilib, audiovizual vositalar o'quvchilarning hissiy tajribasini boshqaradi, deyish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: audiovizual vositalar, muloqot ko'nikmalari, texnik bilimlar, zamonaviy ko'rgazmali qurollar, audiovizual uskunalar, ta'lim olami, hissiy ta'sir.

Аннотация; В этой статье основное внимание уделяется тому, как использовать аудиовизуальные инструменты при преподавании технических курсов на английском языке. Основная цель аудиовизуальных средств – дать возможность учителю сделать обучение эффективным и интересным. Студентам представлены хорошие модели для эффективного обучения. Таким образом, можно сказать, что аудиовизуальные средства направляют сенсорный опыт учащихся.

Ключевые слова: аудиовизуальные средства, коммуникативные навыки, технические знания, современные наглядные средства, аудиовизуальное оборудование, образовательный мир, эмоциональное воздействие.

As we all know that today's age of science and technology. The use of audio visual materials as teaching aids has increased in recent years; thanks to technological

advancement. The teaching learning programs have also been affected by it. The process of teaching-learning depends upon the different type of equipment available in the classroom. Video also plays an important role in the development of creative skills of the trains or unprepared dialogic monologue.

According to studies and research, some teachers claim that whenever they teach with some learning aids, their students get more stimulated because the learning aids help students to become more attentive. Some people are good in retaining information passed to them orally, while some others are extraordinarily good in retaining information through what they read and others through pictures and some other means. But generally, findings and statistics have shown that the best means of facilitating or enhancing good teaching and learning is through the use of instructional materials which encompass audio-visual materials like radio, charts and projectors of various kinds.

In other way most of equipment's instructions are written in English. The use of devices or audio-visual materials will stimulate the greatest number of senses. For this reason, good teachers have always used devices or audio-visual materials. A device is any means, other than the subject-matter to the learner.

In addition, student's positive attitude generates more interest for the lesson they teach, and as a result students participate better in the class. Audio-visuals are useful for most students, regardless of their learning characteristics, when used together. Students will not only hear but also see and make a connection. They will remember what they have seen and recall is so important. In conclusion, we can say audio-visual learning is one of the best methods for teaching students of all ages. People learn in different ways.

In the past the teacher was considered to be the sovereign as far as the teaching – learning process was concerned. The role of the students was mostly passive. Modern trends have changed the face of educational world. Many progressive methods have come in the wake of these trends. Yet the traditional methods are not being given up all together, they are “being modified and adjusted to the changed concepts and situations”. It is new trend to use technology such as videos, televisions and language laboratories in learning how to improve student's skills. By audio-visual methods in teaching we mean the devices that can be used in teaching for their appeal to the ear and the eye. Audio-visual methods in teaching are divided in two categories; simple visual aids and advanced visual aids. Blackboard, bulletin board,

charts, diagrams, graphs, cartoons, posters, maps, pictures, globes and models are simple visual aids which can help in learning how to speed learn. On the other hand televisions and film stripes are advanced visual aids used to train students in the start of their learning, because he or she can learn from the situations. Audio-visual equipment helps the English teacher to make the lesson more demonstrative, interesting indulging and emotional.

Besides, they lesson a tense atmosphere at the lesson and give better results in learning language and remembering the information. Psychologist have proved that a person remembers 10 % – of information from what he reads, 20% – from what he hears, 30% – from what he sees and 40% – from what he does himself. A person can remember more than 50% of information when all senses work in together and when he is involved in the progress. As the popularity of English grows with each passing day and throughout the world, English teachers feel the need to change the methods of teaching their language. There are teachers who use “advanced technology in technological and scientific development”, but most teachers still study in the traditional way.

In practice teachers have come to the same conclusion when they compared the results of different ways of introducing the information. These aids are divided as video, audio and audio-visual aids-video refers as seeing, audio refers as hearing and audio-visual refers to combination of both. These aids are CD, DVD, tape recorder, e-book, graphics, pictures are used to create the requisite interest and motivate the students to learn the language. The visual learning techniques help students to understand and interpret information.

The technique also can provide a structure for writing, reporting, analysis and discussion, and to help focus their thought and ideas.

We know, nowadays English language plays an important role in our life and people need good communication skills in English to prove their knowledge. In order to share or update their technical knowledge, students should know English language. It is clear that visual aids are static; they lack sound and produce great emotional impact on students.

Audio-visual aids are effective tool to impart good education. However, this article does not state that none of these traditional manners are bad or harm to students. In principle, they proved useful today.

There are many opportunities for students to gain confidence in learning English,

which learns language not only for pleasure. For them, in order to keep up with the teaching of English and gain more confidence, they need to move into the world of multimedia technologies.

List of used literatures

1. Joseph Siegel. "Pragmatic Activities for the speaking Classroom".
2. Mannan, A. (2005). *Modern Education: Audio-Visual Aids*. New Delhi.
3. Mayer, R.E., Moreno, R. (2000) 'Engaging students in Active Learning: The case for personalized multimedia messages' *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92.
4. www.studylecturenates.com.